

Supplementary Figure S1. Flow chart of the participant selection process.

Abbreviations: LSG, laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy; %TWL, percent total weight loss.

Supplementary Figure S2. PLS-DA plots showing the differences in steroid profiles between individuals with class II/III obesity and healthy controls under 40 years of age.

Each point represents an individual sample.

Abbreviations: PLS-DA, partial least squares-discriminant analysis.

Supplementary Figure S3. PLS-DA plots showing the differences in steroid profiles of individuals with class II/III obesity before and after LSG.

Each point represents an individual sample.

Abbreviations: PLS-DA, partial least squares-discriminant analysis; LSG, laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy.

Supplementary Table S1. Multiple regression analysis: association between steroid metabolites and variables in men

	Variables	β	SE	<i>P</i> -value
Mineralocorticoids				
11 β -hydroxyprogesterone	Obesity	1.056	0.371	0.006**
	Age	0.02	0.011	0.094
5 α -pregnan-20 α -ol-3-one	Obesity	1.276	0.392	0.002**
	Age	-0.005	0.012	0.701
11-deoxycorticosterone	Obesity	-1.176	0.393	0.004**
	Age	-0.002	0.012	0.885
20 α -hydroxyprogesterone	Obesity	-1.143	0.388	0.005**
	Age	-0.007	0.012	0.545
Glucocorticoids				
11-deoxycortisol	Obesity	1.13	0.391	0.006**
	Age	0.007	0.013	0.588
Sex steroids				
β -estradiol 3-(β -D-glucuronide) 17-sulfate	Obesity	1.286	0.375	0.001**
	Age	0.008	0.012	0.517
Testosterone	Obesity	-1.449	0.38	< 0.001***
	Age	0.008	0.012	0.519
Androsterone glucuronide	Obesity	-1.318	0.366	0.001***
	Age	-0.011	0.011	0.339
Etiocholanolone glucuronide	Obesity	-1.483	0.345	< 0.001***
	Age	-0.012	0.011	0.256

Multiple regression analysis was performed on steroid metabolites with VIP scores >1 and FDR < 0.1 in men with class II/III obesity and healthy controls. Only the metabolites that showed significant differences associated with obesity, independent of age, are shown. **, $P < 0.01$. ***, $P < 0.001$.

Abbreviations: VIP, variable importance in projection; FDR, false discovery rate; SE, standard error.

Supplementary Table S2. Multiple regression analysis: association between steroid metabolites and variables in premenopausal women

	Variables	β	SE	<i>P</i> -value
Mineralocorticoids				
11 β -hydroxyprogesterone	Obesity	1.108	0.273	< 0.001***
	Age	0.006	0.008	0.430
Aldosterone	Obesity	1.698	0.344	< 0.001***
	Age	-0.021	0.015	0.175
11-deoxycorticosterone	Obesity	-1.289	0.385	0.002**
	Age	0.008	0.017	0.660
20 α -hydroxyprogesterone	Obesity	-1.232	0.389	0.003**
	Age	0.005	0.017	0.778
Progesterone	Obesity	-1.343	0.381	0.001**
	Age	0.011	0.017	0.534
Glucocorticoids				
11-deoxycortisol	Obesity	1.181	0.393	0.005**
	Age	-0.008	0.017	0.634
17 α -hydroxypregnenolone	Obesity	-1.318	0.379	0.001**
	Age	-0.001	0.017	0.932
Cortisone	Obesity	-1.064	0.381	0.008**
	Age	-0.024	0.017	0.168
17 α -hydroxyprogesterone	Obesity	-0.985	0.407	0.020*
	Age	0.009	0.018	0.622
Sex steroids				
β -estradiol 3-(β -D-glucuronide) 17-sulfate	Obesity	1.346	0.35	< 0.001***
	Age	0.026	0.015	0.093
Androstenedione	Obesity	-0.793	0.352	0.030*
	Age	-0.053	0.015	0.001**

Multiple regression analysis was performed on steroid metabolites with VIP scores >1 and FDR < 0.1 in premenopausal women with class II/III obesity and healthy controls. Only the metabolites that showed significant differences associated with obesity, independent of age, are shown. *, $P < 0.05$. **, $P < 0.01$. ***, $P < 0.001$.

Abbreviations: VIP, variable importance in projection; FDR, false discovery rate; SE, standard error.

Supplementary Table S3. Characteristics of the individuals with class II/III obesity compared before and after LSG

	Before LSG n = 20	After LSG n = 20	P-value
Age, years	44.5 (43.0-47.3)		
Male, no. (%)	9 (45.0)		
BMI, kg/m ²	40.43 (36.86-45.73)	29.25 (27.92-33.06)	< 0.001***
HbA1c, %	6.2 (5.9-8.4)	5.6 (5.3-6.0)	< 0.001***
FPG, mg/dL	100 (91-132)	98 (90-108)	0.085
C-peptide, ng/mL	3.4 (2.7-3.8)	2.4 (1.7-3.1)	0.024*
TG, mg/dL	116 (94-182)	76 (60-100)	< 0.001***
LDL-C, mg/dL	111 (93-129)	101 (88-123)	0.749
HDL-C, mg/dL	40 (35-49)	62 (52-69)	< 0.001***
SBP, mmHg	134 (129-148)	132 (121-142)	0.688
DBP, mmHg	84 (77-88)	78 (74-88)	0.367
Leptin, ng/mL	37.5 (24.6-53.2)	13.1 (7.8-21.9)	< 0.001***

*, P < 0.05. ***, P < 0.001.

Abbreviations: LSG, laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy; BMI, body mass index; HbA1c, hemoglobin A1c; FPG, fasting plasma glucose; TG, triglycerides; LDL-C, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol; HDL-C, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol; SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure.